

An energy-equivalent cohesive law for modelling z-pinned composite laminates

António R. Melro, Joël Serra,

Giuliano Allegri, Stephen R. Hallett

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Outline

- Introduction to problem
- Multi-scale framework for modelling of z-pinned composites
 - Meso-scale single z-pin testing
 - Micro-scale constitutive bridging model
 - Macro-scale finite element model: Energy-equivalent bridging map
- Experimental validation
- Conclusions

Introduction to problem

- Z-pinning

Image from: Stratton et al., The Rutgers Scholar, 1999

Introduction to problem

- Z-pinning

Image from: I.K. Partridge and S.R. Hallett, Use of microfasteners to produce damage tolerant composite structures, Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A, Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences, 2016

Introduction to problem

- Z-pinning

Images from:

- A.P. Mouritz, Review of z-pinned composite laminates. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 38, pp. 2383-2397, 2007.
- A.P. Mouritz and T.M. Koh, Re-evaluation of mode I bridging traction modelling for z-pinned laminates based on experimental analysis. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 56, pp. 797-807, 2014.

Introduction to problem

- How do we model in FE z-pinned composite laminates?

Multi-scale framework for modelling of z-pinned composites

- Meso-scale single z-pin characterisation

Single z-pin characterisation tests are performed to measure the individual bridging effect of a z-pin as a function of mode-mixity (ϕ).

Multi-scale framework for modelling of z-pinned composites

- Meso-scale single z-pin characterisation

Images from:

Yasaee, M., et al., Experimental characterisation of mixed mode traction–displacement relationships for a single carbon composite Z-pin. *Composites Science and Technology*, 2014. 94: p. 123-131.

Allegri, G., et al., A novel model of delamination bridging via Z-pins in composite laminates. *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 2014. 51(19-20): p. 3314-3332.

Multi-scale framework for modelling of z-pinned composites

- Meso-scale single z-pin characterisation

TTR analytical description:

Euler-Bernoulli beams embedded in an elastic foundation.

Mixed-mode (I-II) response

Equilibrium equations relate opening (W)/sliding (U) displacements to bridging forces exerted by z-pin.

For each mode-mixity, each z-pin length, and z-pin asymmetry, the amount of dissipated energy is calculated, as well as displacement at z-pin pull-out or bending failure.

Image from:

Allegri, G., et al., A novel model of delamination bridging via Z-pins in composite laminates. International Journal of Solids and Structures, 2014. 51(19-20): p. 3314-3332.

Multi-scale framework for modelling of z-pinned composites

- Meso-scale single z-pin characterisation

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Library of Bridging Maps

Multi-scale framework for modelling of z-pinned composites

- Macro-scale finite element model: **Energy-equivalent bridging map**
 - Capture the sequence of events of delamination propagation in a z-pinned laminate,
 - Account for the correct energy dissipated during propagation up to failure, and
 - Identify correct failure mode.

A tri-linear cohesive law is implemented for macro-scale analysis of z-pinned composites

Multi-scale framework for modelling of z-pinned composites

• Macro-scale finite element model: Energy-equivalent bridging map

- **Red area** corresponds to energy dissipated by delamination propagating through the matrix, given by a traditional cohesive zone model;
- **Green area** corresponds to energy dissipated by delamination propagating through the z-pin smeared across the reinforced area;

$$G_{mC}^S = W^P \cdot Z_{AD} \frac{4}{\pi D^2}$$

Multi-scale framework for modelling of z-pinned composites

• Macro-scale finite element model: Energy-equivalent bridging map

- Total area under black curve is the sum of both energies

$$G_{mC}^T = G_{mC}^S + G_{mC}^M$$

- The point of inflection is defined by the displacement at failure of the matrix contribution and by imposing the area under the black curve.

$$\sigma^I = \frac{\sigma_m^{oP} \delta_m^{fP}}{\delta_m^{fP} - \delta_m^{oM}}$$

Multi-scale framework for modelling of z-pinned composites

- Macro-scale finite element model: Energy-equivalent bridging map

Experimental validation

Double Cantilever Beam (DCB)
Mode I

Mixed-Mode Bending (MMB)
Mixed-Mode I/II

End-Loaded Split (ELS)
Mode II

MMB
25%, 47%, and 69%
mode mixity

Experimental validation – mode I

Experimental validation – 25% mode II

Experimental validation – 47% mode II

Experimental validation – 69% mode II

Experimental validation – mode II

Conclusions

- A multi-scale framework has been presented for the numerical modelling of composite laminates reinforced with z-pins.
- An experimental characterisation step at the meso-scale is conducted to identify the bridging properties of an individual z-pin at the mid-plane.
- An analytical model at the micro-scale is used to estimate the energy dissipated by an individual z-pin for any mode mixity, z-pin asymmetry and z-pin length. A library of bridging maps is generated with this information.
- A tri-linear cohesive zone model is developed and implemented in a cohesive element user subroutine that reads from the library of bridging maps as a function of the mode-mixity, z-pin length and z-pin asymmetry.
- The framework was validated against experimental data and an excellent agreement was found on both sequence of damage propagation events and force-displacement curves.

Future Work

- Only the single delamination case was presented here...
- Can this framework be extended to a more general case of multiple delaminations?
- Next presentation by my colleague Joël Serra will answer this question!

Thank you for your attention!

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antonio.melro@bristol.ac.uk

bristol.ac.uk/composites